

Coordination of mono-nucleating Schiff base with Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} ions; derived from 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine, structural aspects and pharmacological properties

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Manuscript received online 03 February 2016, accepted 21 October 2016

Abstract : Fresh series of mononuclear Schiff base Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes have been synthesized with Schiff base derived from 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine, furfuraldehyde and 2,2'-bipyridyl. The chelation of metal complexes has been suggested in analytical, spectral (IR, UV, ESR) and magnetic studies. These data reveal the facts that Schiff base complexes unveil octahedral geometry. Schiff base and its metal complexes have been screened for their antimicrobial (bacteria like *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsilla pneumonia* and the fungi such as *Aspergillus flavu*, *Fusarium oxysporum*) activities. The nucleolytic cleavage activities of complexes were assayed on pUC18 plasmid DNA using gel electrophoresis in the presence of H₂O₂ and the complexes show promising nuclease activity.

Keywords : 4-Nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine, 2,2'-bipyridyl, antimicrobial, *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Introduction

In view of versatile applications of Schiff bases and their metal complexes. Though there is improved research work in the field of coordination chemistry, there remains to be carried out a lot of challenging work on Schiff base metal complexes along with their different industrial and chemotherapeutic studies. Schiff bases derived from amino and carbonyl compounds are an important class of ligands that coordinate with metal ions via azomethine nitrogen and have been studied extensively¹. The π system in a Schiff base often imposes a geometrical constriction and affects the electronic structure as well². In azomethine derivatives, C=N linkage is absolutely necessary for biological activity. Several azomethines were reported to possess remarkable antibacterial, antifungal, anticancer and diuretic activities³⁻⁶. Schiff bases have wide range applications in food industry, dye industry, analytical chemistry, catalysis, fungicidal, agrochemical and biological activities⁷. With the increasing incidence of deep mycosis, more emphasis is laid on the screening

of new and more effective antimicrobial drugs with low toxicity. Schiff base complexes are found as the most important stereo-chemical models in main group and transition metal coordination chemistry due to their structural variety and preparative accessibility⁸. They have played a seminal role in the improvement of modern coordination chemistry. In addition but they can also be found at key points in the development of inorganic biochemistry, catalysis and optical materials⁹.

We report herein the design and synthesis of a new molecular system having both N and O donors in the ligand framework and its reactivity towards Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} ions. Based on the findings of our suggestions are given on a DNA cleavage and antimicrobial activities using synthesized complexes.

Experimental

Materials and physical measurements :

All the chemicals used were highly pure and of AR grade. Solvents were purified and dried in accordance

with the standard procedures. Metal salts were purchased from Merck. 4-Nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine, furfuraldehyde and 2,2'-bipyridyl were bought from Aldrich. Ethanol, DMSO and DMF were used as solvents from Merck and Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd. The purity of metal complexes was tested by TLC. Elemental analyses for C, H and N were carried out using a Perkin-Elmer 2400-II elemental analyzer. UV-Vis spectra were obtained in DMF on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 40 (UV-Vis) spectrometer in the range 200–800 nm. FT-IR data were recorded as KBr disc using Thermo Nicolet, Avatar 370 model spectrometer in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} . Molar conductance of the complexes in DMF was measured using an Elico model conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by employing the Gouy method at room temperature. EPR spectra of compounds were recorded on E-112 ESR spectrometer with X-band microwave frequency (9.5 GHz).

Synthesis of Schiff base :

Schiff base ligand was synthesized by adding 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine (1 mM) in 20 mL of ethanol to furfuraldehyde (2 mM) in 20 mL ethanol. The mixture was refluxed for 2–3 h. Then, solution of the ligand was kept for slow evaporation and the coloured precipitate was collected and dried in air.

Synthesis of mononuclear Schiff base metal complexes :

The ethanolic solution of synthesized ligand (1 mM) was added dropwise stirring in an ethanolic solution of the metal salt (1 mM) with constant stirring followed by the addition of 2,2'-bipyridyl (1 mM) and the mixture was boiled under reflux for 3–5 h. Then, the volume of the reaction mixture was reduced by evaporation. The precipitated complexes were filtered off, washed with ethanol and then dried *in vacuo*.

Antibacterial activity :

The antibacterial activity was carried out at Progen Lab, Salem in Tamilnadu (India). The standard disc-agar diffusion method¹⁰ was followed to determine the activity of synthesized compounds against sensitive organisms. The tested compounds were dissolved in DMF and a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ is obtained. The test was con-

ducted on medium potato dextrose agar containing infusion of 200 g potatoes, 6 g dextrose and 15 g agar. Uniform size filter paper disks (three disks per compound) were infused by equal volume from the specific concentration of dissolved tested compounds and carefully placed on incubated agar surface. After incubation for 36 h at 27 °C, inhibition of the organism which evidenced by clear zone surrounding each disk was measured and used to calculate mean of inhibition zones. Streptomycin was used as a standard.

Antifungal activity :

The fungal cultures were inoculated in nutrient broth (inoculation medium) one day in advance to the experiment and incubated overnight at 37 °C. 24 h grown culture was added aseptically to the nutrient medium and mixed thoroughly in inoculation medium to get uniform distribution. This solution was added slowly (25 mL in each dish) into petri dishes and then permitted to attain

Fig. 1. Proposed structure of Schiff base metal complexes.

room temperature. Wells (6 mm in diameter) were cut in the agar plates using proper sterile tubes. Then, the wells were filled up to the surface of agar with 50 µg/mL of the test compounds dissolved in DMSO. The plates were allowed to stand for an hour in order to facilitate the diffusion of the drug solution. Then the plates were incubated at 37 °C for 48 h for fungi and the diameter of the inhibition zones was measured. The concentration of DMSO in the medium had not affected the growth of any of the microorganisms tested.

Results and discussion

Analytical data of the Schiff base ligands and their mononuclear metal complexes are given in Table 1 and are in well agreement with the expected values. All the Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes are colored, non-hygroscopic solids, stable in air. They are meanly soluble in common organic solvents, but soluble in DMF and DMSO. The solubility of complexes in DMF permitted calculation of molar conductivity (Λ_m) of 10⁻³ M solutions at 25 °C which shows that all the complexes are of 1 : 2 type electrolyte in DMF solution.

common and therefore, only important peaks, shifted or have newly appeared are discussed. Table 2 shows that $\nu(\text{C-O})$ and $\nu(\text{C=N})$ modes occur at 1297–1338 cm⁻¹ and 1612–1666 cm⁻¹ respectively. The shifting of (C-O) towards higher frequency as compared to the ligand 1297 cm⁻¹ is due to conversion of hydrogen bonded structure into a covalent metal bonded structure. Lowering of (C=N) in the complexes as compared to the ligand (1666 cm⁻¹) is due to reduction of double bond character of carbon-nitrogen bond of the azomethine group. These results predict that acetate ions were coordinated outside the coordination sphere. Metal-ligand bond is further confirmed by the appearance of a medium intensity band in the range 448–468 and 530–567 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of complexes assigned to stretching frequencies of (M-N) bond and metal-oxygen bond formation respectively¹².

Electronic spectra and magnetic moment :

Table 3, a clear view of electronic spectral data of metal complexes in DMF solution are arrayed. From an electronic spectra the nature of the ligand field around metal ion was deduced. The electronic spectrum of Co^{II} complex exhibited three bands in the region of 615, 575

Table 1. Analytical data of the Schiff base ligand and its mononuclear metal complexes

Molecular formula	Colour	Yield (%)	Melting point (°C)	Found (Calcd.) (%)				Molar conductance Λ_m (S cm ² mol ⁻¹)
				C	H	N	Metal	
C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄	Yellow	84	143	62.14 (62.13)	3.59 (3.58)	13.15 (13.18)	-	-
Cu(C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄)	Green	76	> 200	59.04 (59.03)	3.63 (3.62)	13.31 (13.30)	12.30 (12.28)	13.12
Ni(C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄)	Brown black	72	> 200	59.58 (59.57)	3.66 (3.65)	13.39 (13.37)	11.21 (11.20)	11.32
Co(C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄)	Brown	75	> 200	59.56 (59.55)	3.66 (3.65)	13.40 (13.41)	11.26 (11.24)	9.86
Mn(C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄)	Black	69	> 200	60.02 (60.00)	3.67 (3.68)	13.49 (13.47)	10.56 (10.55)	10.32

IR spectra :

IR spectra provide valuable information regarding coordinating sites of Schiff base ligand which has been already discussed by Raman *et al.*¹¹. IR spectra of the complexes were compared with that of free ligand to determine changes that might have taken place during complexation. A comparative study of IR spectra of ligand and its metal complexes reveals that certain peaks are

Table 2. Infrared spectroscopic data of the Schiff base ligand and its mononuclear metal complex

Compound	(C=N) (cm ⁻¹)	(C-O) (cm ⁻¹)	(M-N) (cm ⁻¹)	(M-O) (cm ⁻¹)
C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄	1624	1297	-	-
Cu(C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄)	1612	1315	448	530
Ni(C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄)	1617	1338	465	558
Co(C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄)	1666	1329	468	567
Mn(C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄)	1614	1334	451	560

Table 3. Electronic spectral data of Schiff base ligand and its complexes

Compound	Electronic spectra (nm)				Geometry of the complex
	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$	L \rightarrow M	d-d	
$C_{16}H_{11}N_3O_4$	293	383	-	-	-
$Cu(C_{26}H_{19}N_5O_4)$	282	352	474	637,575,536	Octahedral
$Ni(C_{26}H_{19}N_5O_4)$	268	363	448	648,581,531	
$Co(C_{26}H_{19}N_5O_4)$	277	382	460	615,575,560	
$Mn(C_{26}H_{19}N_5O_4)$	282	363	439	617,552,533	

and 560 nm which were assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions, respectively. The value of magnetic moment 4.97 B.M. indicates presence of Co^{II} complex in octahedral geometry¹³. The electronic spectrum of Ni^{II} complex showed three bands at 648, 581 and 531 nm assignable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions, respectively. The value of magnetic moment was 3.33 B.M.; therefore, an octahedral geometry is suggested for this complex¹⁴. The 2E_g and ${}^2T_{2g}$ states of the octahedral Cu^{II} (d^9) split under the effect of tetragonal distortion and the distortion can be such as to cause the three transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ to remain unresolved in the spectra. It is determined that all three transitions 637, 575 and 536 nm lie within the single broad envelope centered at the same range mentioned earlier. This assignment is in agreement with the general observation that Cu^{II} d-d transitions are normally close in energy. The magnetic moment of 2.01 B.M. falls within the range normally observed for octahedral Cu^{II} complexes¹⁵. The electronic spectra of Mn^{II} complexes show absorption bands in the range of 617, 552 and 533 nm. These absorption bands may be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g}$ transitions, respectively. These bands suggest that the complexes possess an octahedral geometry. The magnetic moment of Mn^{II} complex at room temperature is 5.98 B.M., corresponding to five unpaired electrons which suggest octahedral geometry¹⁶. In the spectra of Schiff base ligand, absorption band observed at 268–293 nm were assigned to intra-ligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition and the band at 352–383 nm were assigned due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition associated with azomethine chromophore ($-C=N$).

EPR spectra :

EPR spectra of complexes provide information of im-

portance in studying the metal ion environment. EPR spectra of $[Cu(C_{26}H_{19}N_5O_4)]$ Schiff base complexes recorded on powder samples with room temperature on X-band at frequency 9.3 GHz under the magnetic field strength 4000 G.

EPR spectrum of $Cu(C_{26}H_{19}N_5O_4)$ as shown in Fig. 2 shows a broad signal with g_{iso} at 2.0002 which is consistent with an octahedral geometry¹⁷.

Fig. 2. EPR spectra of $[Cu(C_{26}H_{19}N_5O_4)]$ complex.

Antibacterial studies :

The synthesized ligand and its mononuclear metal complexes are tested for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity. Significant inhibitory data is observed in Table 4. The susceptibilities of certain strains of Gram-positive (*Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*) and Gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Klebsilla pneumonia*) cultures to Schiff base and their complexes are evaluated by the measurement of the size of bacteriostatic diameter. The increase in the activity occurs due to structures of Schiff base ligand by possessing an azomethine ($C=N$) linkage. The toxic activity of complexes with the ligand can be ascribed to increase in lipophilic nature of complexes arising from chelation¹⁸. The mode of action of complexes involves formation of hydrogen bonds with the imino group by the active sites leading to interference

Table 4. Antibacterial activity of ligand and its metal complexes

Compound	Diameter of inhibition zone (mm)			
	Gram-positive bacteria		Gram-negative bacteria	
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Klebsilla pneumonia</i>
C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄	+	+	+	+
Cu(C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄)	++++	++++	+++	+++
Ni(C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄)	+++	+++	++	++
Co(C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄)	++	++	++	++
Mn(C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄)	+++	+++	++	++
Streptomycin	++++	++++	++++	++++

Zone of inhibition diameter in mm (% inhibition) : - (0%); +, 6–10 (27–45%); ++, 10–14 (45–64%); +++, 14–18 (64–82%); +++++, 18–22 (82–100%). Inhibition percentages are relative to the zone of inhibition of the most active compound (22 mm) with 100% inhibition.

with cell wall synthesis. This hydrogen bond formation damages cytoplasmic membrane and cell permeability may also be resulting in the death of the cell. The higher activity of Cu(C₂₆H₁₉N₅O₄) complex can be explained as on chelation. The polarity of Cu(C₂₆H₁₉N₅O₄) ion is found to be reduced to a greater extent due to overlapping of the ligand orbital and partial sharing of the positive charge of copper ion with donor groups. Therefore, Cu(C₂₆H₁₉N₅O₄) ions are adsorbed onto the surface of cell wall of microorganisms. The adsorbed Cu(C₂₆H₁₉N₅O₄) ions disturb the respiratory process of the cells, thus, blocking synthesis of proteins and this, in turn restricts further growth of the organisms¹⁹.

Antifungal activity :

Antifungal activity of ligand and its metal chelates were shown in Fig. 4. From the results obtained by the antifun-

gal activity, it is proved beyond doubt that the metal complexes are more active against all tested fungi than the ligands²⁰. The greater activity of these complexes is probably due to variation in structure on coordination. The result may be in inhibitory or reductions in toxicology of metal ions towards some organisms.

Fig. 4. Antifungal activity of Schiff base ligand and its metal complexes against fungal strains

Fig. 3. Antibacterial activity of Schiff base ligand and its metal complexes against bacterial strains.

DNA cleavage :

Gel electrophoresis experiments were completed using pUC18DNA with ligand complexes in the presence and absence of H₂O₂. Complexes exhibit cleavage ability at low concentration (40 μM). When calf-thymus DNA is subjected to electrophoresis, relatively fast migration will take place for the intact super coil form (Form I). If scission occurs on one strand (nicking), the super coil will relax to generate a slower moving open circular form (Form II). When both strands are cleaved, a linear form

(Form III) migrating between Forms I and II will be generated²¹. Fig. 5 shows more activity in the presence of oxidant which may be due to the reaction of hydroxyl radical with DNA. The results of DNA cleavage are already shown in Fig. 5. All metal complexes were able to alter DNA (Form I) into open circular (Form II). The mononuclear Cu^{II} complex was found to be highly active in cleaving DNA in the presence of hydrogen peroxide.

Fig. 5. Changes in the agarose gel electrophoretic pattern of pUC18DNA induced by H₂O₂ and metal complexes. Lane 1 - DNA alone; Lane 2 - DNA alone + H₂O₂; Lane 3 - DNA + Cu complex + H₂O₂; Lane 4 - DNA + Ni complex + H₂O₂; Lane 5 - DNA + Co complex; Lane 6 - DNA + Mn complex + H₂O₂.

Conclusions

The present study proves that octahedral geometry is around Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes coordinating through nitrogen and oxygen atoms. The observations of antimicrobial activity prove that the compounds exhibit antimicrobial properties and it is important to note that the metal chelates show more inhibitory effects than the parent ligand. DNA cleavage studies notice that all the complexes significantly cleave the DNA molecule.

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